

Reactions of the Cobaltic Ion. Part-I. The Reactions of the Cobaltic Ion with Water

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The kinetics of the reduction of cobalt (III) generated *in situ* by the interaction of potassium cobalt (III) carbonate and sulphuric acid have been examined. The effect of (H⁺), (Co⁺⁺), (F⁻) and (Ag⁺) has also been studied in brief. The values of energy and entropy of activation have been calculated.

Cobalt (III) remains stable to some extent in highly acidified solutions of perchloric, sulphuric, or acetic acid. In dilute acids, oxygen is evolved and cobalt (III) is reduced to cobalt (II) state. Several workers¹⁻⁵ have reported the kinetics of the reduction of electrolytically prepared cobalt (III) in acidic medium. It has been observed that when potassium cobalt (III) carbonate is mixed with sulphuric acid, cobalt (III) sulphate is generated *in situ*. The present investigation has been undertaken to find out its nature and applicability for the kinetic studies of the oxidation of a few organic compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were AnalaR or equivalent grade. Fresh solutions of potassium cobalt (III) carbonate were prepared by the method of Laitinen and Burdett⁶. The conical flask, containing a calculated quantity of the complex was wrapped with black cloth to avoid the photochemical effect. It was then immersed in a low temperature thermostat maintained at the desired temperature. In the other flask a calculated quantity of H₂SO₄ (so as to produce a desired excess of the acid in the reaction mixture, when the two solutions were mixed and cobalt (III) carbonate was completely converted to cobalt (III) sulphate) was taken.

The solutions in the said flasks after attaining the temperature of the bath, were mixed together and shaken vigorously to remove the carbon dioxide gas. In all the runs, total volume of the reaction mixture was 100 ml. The time of mixing the two solutions was noted and aliquots of reaction mixture were withdrawn at different intervals of time and estimated iodometrically.

The reaction was found to be very fast on immediate mixing due to local heating produced by neutralisation of the bi-carbonate with the acid, but after 10 mins. the reaction becomes regular.

1. Oberer, Dissertation, Basle, 1903.
2. Noyes and Deahl, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 1337.
3. Weiss, *Naturwiss.*, 1935, **23**, 64.
4. Bawn and White, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 331.
5. Baxendale and Wells, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 800.
6. Laitinen and Burdett, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 1268.

RESULTS

The kinetic studies of the reduction of electrolytically prepared cobalt (III) have been reported by several workers¹⁻⁵. The data for the corresponding studies on cobalt (III) generated *in situ* have not, therefore, been given. And only the results have been summarised.

The reduction of cobalt (III) in lower concentrations of sulphuric acid follows a second order kinetics and an increase in its concentration decreases the velocity of the reaction. It has been observed, however, that if the concentration of sulphuric acid is lower than 0.50 *N*, the second order constants tend to increase showing that order of the reaction is less than two. These results are, therefore, not contradictory to the observations of Bawn and White⁴. If, however, the concentration of sulphuric acid is increased to more than 2*N*, the second order rate constants tend to fall off rapidly, indicating that in higher concentrations of the acid, the reaction becomes of a still higher order (Cf. Oberer, Dissertation, Basle, 1903).

Again, there has been a progressive decrease in the reaction rate with increase of time. But this cannot be ascribed to the progressive formation of cobalt (II) generated *in situ* from the reduction of cobalt (III) since even ten fold increase in cobalt (II) ion concentration has little depressing effect on the rate of the reduction. A small variation in the ionic species as effected by the addition of fluoride or silver ions has specific influence in enhancing the rate though nature of the reaction remains unaffected (cf. Kirwin and Sutcliffe, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 2288).

It has been noticed that if the reaction is carried out at 5°, even 2.25*N* sulphuric acid is sufficient to check the decomposition of 1.25×10^{-3} *M* cobalt (III). At higher temperatures addition of concentrated solution of the acid is, however, necessary. The average values of temperature-coefficient and energy of activation for the reaction (between 30° and 40°) are 3.96 and 25.75 K.cals. mole⁻¹, respectively. The average values of frequency-factor and entropy of activation are 1.63×10^{17} litres mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹, and +19.27 e.u. respectively.

The nature of cobalt (III) generated *in situ* by the interaction of potassium cobalt (III) carbonate and sulphuric acid is similar to that prepared by electrolytic method. It has, therefore, been used in the kinetic studies of the oxidation of organic compounds to be reported in subsequent communications.

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